

ST cluster 6

ST cluster 25

ST cluster 48

ST cluster 5

ST cluster 1

Figure S1. Dendrogram constructed from concatenated nucleotide sequence data for the 30 study isolates as well as 386 publicly-available concatenated MLST sequences for *Staphylococcus* chromogenes. Study isolates which grouped together with a bootstrap value of $\geq 65\%$ were classified as ST clusters, and are highlighted by a red rectangle. The tree was constructed using a maximum-likelihood algorithm with the optimal model and 100 bootstrap replications in MEGA-X (Kumar et al., 2018).